

Moderation Effect of Information Network Centrality – The Relationship Between Positive Psychological Capital And Entrepreneurial Hustle

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Abstract

The current study explains the relationship between Positive psychological capital and Entrepreneurial hustle and further explains the moderation role of Information network centrality on the relationship between Positive psychological capital and Entrepreneurial hustle through mindset theory. A Survey technique was used for the collection of required data. Questionnaires were collected from 185 entrepreneurs surveying in Quetta and proposed relationships were analyzed through SMART-PLS structural equation modeling software because it is the second generation technique of multivariate data analysis. This study found a significant positive relationship between Positive psychological capital (Hope, self-efficacy, resilience, optimism) and Entrepreneurial hustle. The results also revealed that Information network centrality as a moderator strengthens the relationship between Positive psychological capital and Entrepreneurial hustle. The role of independent and dependent variables was assigned to the construct through mindset theory. Positive psychological capital, Entrepreneurial hustle, and

Information network centrality, all three multidisciplinary constructs are relatively new and no previous research discusses the relationship between these three constructs. This is the first study that discusses the relationship between these constructs. This study addresses a gap by creating an understanding of entrepreneurial actions in the context of uncertainty.

Keywords - Positive psychological capital, Entrepreneurial hustle, Information network centrality

1. Introduction

Entrepreneurship is considered one of the key motivating facets of socio-economic growth. Entrepreneurs play a significant role in the economic advancement of the country as of their incredible contributions to economic progress (Bărbulescu et al., 2021). The entrepreneur comprises the creation of innovative ventures and development of them into effective and workable organizations. (Coulibaly et al., 2018). Entrepreneurs are innovators because innovation is the hallmark of entrepreneurship. Entrepreneurs are a unique group of people, who generate ideas and turn these innovative ideas into reality. They are prone to take risk of starting new businesses and taking the sole responsibility of managing the business successfully (Khalil et al., 2021).

In the new digital and technological economy, where the workers are decentralized and firms focus on productivity and creativity, the word “hustler” or “hustler mentality” is being considered for entrepreneurship. It is observed that Hustlers and entrepreneurs use different techniques and strategies different from other’s people to earn profit. This concept differentiates the hustling people from other groups. This small group is different from others in respect of hardworking and taking risks. Thus “hustler” is another form of Entrepreneurship (Pengilly, 2009).

Entrepreneurship hustle is an entrepreneur’s untraditional, critical and urgent actions that are proposed in crisis and uncertain situations where urgent decisions are required to capture the

opportunities and handle the difficult situation (Fisher et al., 2020). Entrepreneurship is the formation and development of new products and ideas which contains uncertainty (Townsend et al., 2018). In addition, Fisher et al. (2020) found five concepts related to Entrepreneurial hustle are, (1) hustle for opportunities, (2) hustle for resources, (3) Hustle for Entrepreneurial learning, (4) Hustle for legitimacy and (5) hustle for connections.

Further, investment plays a vital role in the success of any business. Investment is not only limited to tangible resources such as financial and physical resources instead it also includes intangible resources too (Fang et al., 2021). Entrepreneurship is a highly stressful occupation involving undertaking risks and often demanding workloads; hence requiring mental inputs like psychological capital (Baluku et al., 2018). Therefore, Psychological capital is an intangible resource important for entrepreneurs to face the challenges of entrepreneurship and increase their survival chances. Psychological capital is relatively a new term used in different (human Capital, financial Capital, technological Capital, physical Capital, intellectual and social capital) forms of capital (Baluku et al., 2018).

Psychological capital represents what people are likely to attain with, as Contrasting to what they are likely to accomplish without. "HERO" This acronym stands for four positive cognitive resources of psychological capital: Hope, Efficacy, Resiliency, and Optimism (Ribeiro et al., 2021). In psychological capital, the focus is on "who you are" which is a considerable factor for individual self-development. Positive psychological factors discuss the person's strengths in contrast with their weaknesses (Jin, 2017). Positive psychological capital enables the entrepreneur to understand "who you are" and go forward with Entrepreneurial hustle. Create opportunities, and dare to take the risk, no need to be fearful. Do what you want to do and achieve success.

Additionally, an Entrepreneur's behavior is most important in entrepreneurship, which creates things that previously existed nothing. Who bears the responsibility for his actions and take risk in an uncertain context. The main focus of entrepreneurship action theories is to understand the behavior which determines an entrepreneur's action (Fisher et al., 2020). Positive psychological capital is related to hustler entrepreneurship as its five subconcepts are directly influenced by Positive psychological capital. The entrepreneur with high hope, self-efficacy, resilience and optimism can create opportunities and take risks in an uncertain business situation, accept challenges with courage, can tolerate the pressure of the uncertain market situation and take advantage of timely taking decisions (Joseph et al., 2021). The person with high Positive psychological capital can find alternative ways to arrange the required resources through networking with partners or stakeholders because he believes there are many solutions for a single problem, and only need to think out of the box.

Further, According to (Khayru et al., 2021) the main concern of entrepreneurs is relevant and reliable Information searching because it helps in better decision making by reducing irrelevant information and uncertainty (Purbasari et al., 2021). Information network centrality enables entrepreneurs to self-evaluation their perceptions about others. Also, Information network centrality plays a vital role to reduce the uncertainty of the entrepreneur and able him to take timely decisions in an uncertain context. The limited research conducted on moderating role of network centrality (Wang et al., 2020).

In this study, we examined the Positive psychological capital as an independent variable that affects the Entrepreneurial hustle dependent variable moderated by Information network centrality in the context of uncertainty, which results contribute to theoretical significance.

Research Objectives

1. To examine the relationship between Positive psychological capital and Entrepreneurial hustle.
2. To explore the moderation effect of Information network centrality on the relationship between Positive psychological capital and Entrepreneurial hustle.

Problem Statement

The notion of Positive psychological capital was introduced in 2004 (Nolzen, 2018), and Entrepreneurial hustle in 2020 (Fisher et al., 2020), both concepts are new and no previous studies discuss the relationship between these variables. Further, entrepreneurs are interested to gain quick, reliable information from different sources related to their business which in results reduces uncertainty and identifies opportunities. Limited research is conducted on the moderating role of Information network centrality. All three multidisciplinary construct are relatively new and no previous research discusses the relationship between these constructs. So, the Literature gap is huge and still need to be learned about the relationship between these construct. Our study expands the body of knowledge by finding the relationship between Positive psychological capital and Entrepreneurial hustle. Further to explore the moderation effect of Information network centrality on the relationship between Positive psychological capital and Entrepreneurial hustle.

Research Gap

This study addresses a gap by creating an understanding of entrepreneurial actions in the context of uncertainty. As we know entrepreneurship requires actions but literature is not sufficient on what actions an entrepreneur will take in the context of uncertainty to minimize the risk. This shows a significant shortcoming in the body of knowledge. This study provides valuable insights into the literature by highlighting entrepreneurial actions in uncertainty.

Significance of the Study

In this study, we identify the role of variables, Positive psychological capital as an independent variable, Entrepreneurial hustle as a dependent variable, and Information network centrality as a moderator variable through Entrepreneurial mindset theory which states entrepreneurial mindset develops as how's one thinking and state of mind consciously or unconsciously or the perception through which entrepreneur analyze the world and stimuli one's tendency for entrepreneurial activities and consequences. It denotes that employing an entrepreneurial mindset directs an entrepreneur to take entrepreneurial action in the context of uncertainty and an unorthodox environment(Reed & Stoltz, 2011).The idea of an entrepreneurial mindset in business literature is established on the cognitive process of how individuals observe, link, and process information about his / herself, others, related tasks, and uncertain situations which determine the actions of entrepreneurs(Kouakou et al., 2019).

In addition, the current study will contribute by providing a new theoretical framework consisting of all these variables that can be used to analyze the relationship between the variables.

Also, this study focuses on multidisciplinary construct and their relationship which results contribute to the literature and provide insights for future research.

2. Literature Review

Entrepreneurship is an emerging field. Its wide-ranging, multifaceted and versatile nature makes it challenging to consider all aspects of entrepreneurship (Busenitz et al., 2003; Murphy et al., 2006), That's why researchers lack a universal definition of this discipline (Morrison, 2006). This field is discussed by different researchers observing different perspectives and conceptualizing, there are no universal criteria to define the entrepreneurship and entrepreneur's role. That's the reason different scholars formulate different definitions according to their perspectives (Kouakou et al., 2019).

Every phase of the entrepreneurial process encounters numerous challenges combined with a challenging competitive work environment and risk associated with dynamic businesses (Baron et al., 2016; Umukoro & Okurame, 2017). Entrepreneurs are known as innovators because idea creation is the hallmark of entrepreneurship. In this context, entrepreneurs are demonstrated by a unique group of persons who take the initiative to turn ideas into functional form and are solely responsible for the administrative and managerial functions of the organizations. Entrepreneurs are innovators because they are concerned with creating new ideas. In this sense of the word, entrepreneurs are considered a unique group of individuals who take initiative in turning business ideas into a reality. This is done by assuming the risk of a new business and being solely responsible for its operation and management (Ratten, 2022).

Normally, In Entrepreneurship most of the questions are enquired is: who is capable to be Entrepreneur? How do they act and think differently in analyzing different Opportunities? How do Entrepreneurs achieve their goals differently? This is because entrepreneurship covers a wide range of fields like Economics, Psychology, Business, and Sociology, that's why several approaches are used to understand the dynamic concept of Entrepreneurship (Hisrich et al., 2007). The answer to these queries is still blurred and overlapped with other subfields.

2.1. Origin of Entrepreneurship

The word "Entrepreneur" appear 1st time in 1253 in literature. It is a French word, derived from the verb "entrepreneur" which means "undertaker" and represents any person who is undertaking any substantial project. The philosophical thoughtfulness of three authors, Jean Baptist say, Richard Cantillon, and Joseph Alois Schumpeter were the leading pioneers who describe the role of entrepreneurs in their writings extensively (Kouakou et al., 2019).

Historical evolutions of ideas about entrepreneurship are wide-ranging and can be organized in different ways, issue by issue, period by period and theorist by theorist. (Ricketts, 2009).

The concept of entrepreneurship which is prevailing now days was not developed in the ancient and mediaeval era (Springborg, 1987). In the Aristotelian tradition, static societies prevailed on the cast and social position in which honorable fighters and agriculture were respected and commerce was ignored. In the medieval period, religious scholars prohibit Usury (interest on a loan) so society prefer afterward life instead of material things in this world which hamper the concept of Entrepreneurship (McKelvey, 2004). Further, in the late fifteenth century, with the upswing of modern states of Spain, France, and England to protect their interest, leaders no longer trust medieval obligations. The significant concern lies in the Structure of the power and income of the nation. Therefore 16th and 17th centuries were more encouraging to entrepreneurship (Borscheid & Haueter, 2012). Finally 18th and 19th centuries in which the agriculture and industrial revolution take place produced the modern and dynamic concept of Entrepreneurship. From this era, the idea of heroic Entrepreneur developed and entrepreneurs started to be studied and respected (Ahmed & McQuaid, 2005).

2.2. Hustle

Normally, “hustle” means to act immediately, quickly, hurried and aggressively in business. The slang word which is used negatively to get something from any one in unethical way or use any mean to gain those resources. But Aggression in business settings is culture and context specific as in America, aggression in business practices is not considered as negative thing instead it is reflected as distinctive characteristic which distinguish leaders from losers. Hustlers reject the old traditional practices of old generation and find licit work (Thieme, 2013, 2015).

In addition, the hustle is described as strategic opportunistic. “hustle” is paradoxical, on one side it is revealed the state of being out of place of the current place and on the other hand it was situated and place-based (Thieme, 2013). The limited access to legal resources and formal

methods of workforces youth to move from shaky to survival places where they embrace livelihood strategies that are frequently surrounded by opportunism “Jugaad” because of hardship and scarce resources (Jeffrey, 2010). This behavior generate alternative way of learning and doing the things differently where economic transactions depend on particular interpersonal ties (McFarlane, 2011) .

Now days, many web bloggers use this word as a way of living rather than of a single activity; it is normally called hustling mentality (Hustler, 2008). The “hustler mentality” when two words merged give different interpretation as it is a way of thinking, thoughtfulness or implications of a frame of mind which share the same values of entrepreneurship like innovative ideas, autonomy, risk-taking, capture opportunities for successful ventures (Pengilly, 2009). In addition, It is observed that Hustlers and entrepreneurs use different techniques and strategies different from other’s people to earn profit. This concept differentiates the hustling people from other group. This small group is different from others in respect of hardworking and taking risk. Thus “hustler” is another form of Entrepreneurship (Pengilly, 2009).

2.3. Entrepreneurial hustle

“Entrepreneurial hustle is an entrepreneur’s urgent, unorthodox actions that are intended to be useful in addressing immediate challenges and opportunities under conditions of uncertainty” (Fisher et al., 2020). Hustling entrepreneurship is an entrepreneur’s untraditional, critical and urgent actions that are proposed in situation of crisis and uncertain situations where urgent decisions are required to capture the opportunities and handle the difficult situation (fisher Greg, 2021). Entrepreneurship is creation and development of new products and ideas which contains uncertainty (Townsend et al., 2018). Fisher et al. (2020) found five concepts related to Entrepreneurial hustle are

(1) *Hustle for Opportunity*

Represent, identification and exploitation of opportunities through hustle(Alvarez & Barney, 2007) and exposure to new markets (Lumpkin & Dess, 1996)

(2) *Hustle for Resources*

States building something from nothing. *By* using hustle to scare resources which is at disposable or to arrange the acquisition of resources to overcome the shortage of resources (Baker & Nelson, 2005).

(3) *Hustle for Learning*

States hustle to learn about target customer, product innovation and engaging in hustle represents as to know about customers, outcomes, formation of product and positioning in market fit (Shepherd & Gruber, 2021; Wood et al., 2019).

(4) *Hustle for Legitimacy*

States considering such actions which makes new ventures credible and legitimate to the market(Fisher et al., 2017; Zott & Huy, 2007).

(5) *Hustle for Connections*

Represent establishing connections and ties with stake holders. Engage in such activities which strengthen the ties with supporters (Vissa, 2011).

2.3. Positive psychological capital

Positive psychological capital describes an individual's psychological capacity that can be measured, developed, and managed for performance improvement (Nolzen, 2018). Psychological capital is stated to as the "HERO within" (Luthans & Youssef-Morgan, 2017; Satpathy, 2020), representing as what people are likely to attain with, as Contrasting to what they are likely to accomplish without, positive psychological resources. This acronym stands for four positive cognitive resources of psychological capital: Hope, Efficacy, Resiliency, and Optimism.

Hope is determination to accomplish the designated goals and if any hurdles distract him, try to resolve the issues and redirect the means to achieve the desired goals. Efficacy denotes the self-trust or self believe that one can overcome in challenging and uncertain situations with required efforts. Resilience stands for one's ability to don't give up instead recover quickly after failure, discouragement, bounce back, try with improved and positive changes. Optimism represent being positive in achieving realistic outcome in present and future (Luthans et al., 2007).

2.4. Information network centrality

Network centrality is venture's position within the whole network of ties, that consists a network and shows the focal venture's structural position in contrast with other firms in the network(El-Khatib et al., 2015). In addition, the position of ego in the network ties is explained by network centrality. The hub position of the ego in a network is associated with less reliance on a single source(Bizzi, 2022).

According to (Alvarez & Busenitz, 2001), the main concern of entrepreneur is relevant and reliable Information searching because it helps in better decision making by reducing the irrelevant information and uncertainty (McMullen & Shepherd, 2006; Shane & Venkataraman, 2000). As mentioned by network experts about network centrality that different positions of the entrepreneurs in a network signify by different access to valuable information for decision in uncertain context (Ibarra & Andrews, 1993).

An entrepreneur who is in a hub position can control and manage the information accordingly. An entrepreneur who has a central position in a network has the advantage of quick access to information and the opportunity to assemble and compare different pieces of relevant information through different sources(Mehra et al., 2001).According to Van Burg et al. (2021), a reliable entrepreneur who has high social status and a reputation in entrepreneurial ties is in a

better position to obtain critical, important and sufficient information which is helpful for an entrepreneur to decide in an unclear situation.

3. Theoretical Framework

3.1. Mindset Theory

The entrepreneurial mindset in business writings is established on the cognitive process of how individuals observe, link, and process information about his / herself, others, related tasks, and uncertain situations which determine the actions of entrepreneurs (Kouakou et al., 2019). In this model, Positive psychological capital (PsyCap) is the cognitive capabilities of the entrepreneur, the process of information is represented by Information network centrality and Entrepreneurial hustle is the actions of the entrepreneur.

The notion of an entrepreneurial mindset is explained by a state of mind which changes individual behavior into entrepreneurial behavior. Through state of mind an individual act as an entrepreneur and analyze the situations to capture opportunities (Reed & Stoltz, 2011)

The entrepreneurship mindset is all about achieving the objectives by converting ideas into reality by analysis of the world, the world's opportunities and means to capture those opportunities, and how one individual contributes to the socio-economic system and construct a conducive environment (Ferrero & Fioro, 2014). According to McGrath and MacMillan (2000) formulated an entrepreneurial mindset explanation grounded on three factors; the capability to intellect, the capacity to act quickly, and the aptitude to generate resources even in unclear and ambiguous situations. Additionally growth-oriented perspective of mindset is another way to define it.

Therefore a mutual understanding of entrepreneurial mindset appears as how one thinking and state of mind is consciously and unconsciously or the perception through which an entrepreneur analyzes the world and stimuli one's tendency for entrepreneurial activities and

outcomes. It denotes that employing an entrepreneurial mindset directs an entrepreneur to take entrepreneurial action in the context of uncertainty and an unorthodox environment (Reed & Stoltz, 2011). This model developed through mindset theory as in this model PsyCap is an individual's state of mind and Entrepreneurial hustle is entrepreneur's actions which are determined by an individual's perceptions about the world and thorough information on how one analyzes and captures the opportunities in an unorthodox way in an uncertain context.

3.2. Hypotheses

Generally "hustle" means to act immediately, quickly, hurried and aggressively in business. Aggression in business settings is culture and context-specific. Hustlers reject the old traditional practices of the old generation and find licit work (Thieme, 2013, 2015). This concept differentiates the hustling people from other groups. This small group is different from others in respect of hardworking and taking risks (Pengilly, 2009). Positive psychological capital describes an individual's psychological capacity that can be measured, developed, and managed for

performance improvement in an unorthodox environment (Nolzen, 2018). The Positive psychological capital of an entrepreneur is explained by the state of mind which changes individual behavior into entrepreneurial behavior. Through state of mind an individual act as an entrepreneur and analyze the situations to capture opportunities (Reed & Stoltz, 2011). Positive psychological capital includes hope, efficacy, resilience, and optimism, if the entrepreneur has high hope (to complete the task), efficacy (self believe), resilience (strike back) and optimism change entrepreneurial actions in an uncertain environment. The entrepreneur with Positive psychological capital can create opportunities and take risks in uncertain business situations, accept challenges with courage, can tolerate the pressure of uncertain market situations, and take advantage of timely taking decisions. From the above arguments, it is evident Positive psychological capital plays an important role in hustling entrepreneurship. Thus, based on the above literature, the following is suggested

H1: Positive psychological capital is positively related to Entrepreneurial hustle.

Network position is an actor's comparative position in the group (Wasko & Faraj, 2005). Through a central position, entrepreneurs access and control more information that may alter their self-evaluation and perceptions about other individuals' behaviors (Lee et al., 2010). New studies discovered the direct effect of Network centrality on an entrepreneur's performance (Hornig 2016; Lu, 2011). Limited research was conducted on moderating the role of network centrality (Wang et al., 2020) (Wasko & Faraj, 2005).

According to (Alvarez & Busenitz, 2001), the main concern of many entrepreneurs is relevant and reliable Information searching because it helps in better decision making by reducing irrelevant information and uncertainty (McMullen & Shepherd, 2006; Shane & Venkataraman, 2000). From the above literature, it is concluded that Information network

centrality enables entrepreneurs to self-evaluation their perceptions about others. Also, Information network centrality plays a vital role to reduce the uncertainty of the entrepreneur and able him to take the timely decision in an uncertain context. Thus based on literature, the following is suggested:

H2:Information network centrality moderates the relationship between Positive psychological capital and Entrepreneurial hustle.

4. Research Methodology

a. Nature of the Study

The current study is of quantitative in nature because the researcher collects the required data from respondents through a questionnaire which is comprised of numeric form. Additionally, it follows positivism research philosophy and a deductive approach is used as hypotheses were tested.

b. Research Design

The population of this research is entrepreneurs of the Quetta city. The researcher used non-probability, Convenience sampling techniques because, in social sciences, the non-probability convenience sampling technique is most appropriate (Palys, 2008).The sample size was collected through Cochran's (1963), “ $N_0 = Z^2pq / e^2$ ” equation to calculate the suitable sample size that explains the appropriate pool of target participants for the study. According to Israel (1992) when the population is unknown, this equation method is most appropriate to calculate the adequate sample size for the study is 384.

c. Data Collection

According to Saunders et al. (2009), two types of data collection method is available for research consist primary and secondary data. In this study, the researcher used the primary source of data collection method through survey method to achieve the relevant information related to the study which is a time, cost-effective and definitive method to collect data. The data was gathered through the survey method, 400 Questionnaires were circulated and the google dox link was shared with entrepreneurs. Questionnaires were given to the entrepreneurs and later gathered from them. 190 questionnaires were considered for this study which is dully filled by the participants. In total, 30.5 % respondents were female and 60.5 % respondents were male. Out of the total, 3.7% had degree below matric, 5.3% had intermediate degree, 41%, 30.5 %, 17 %, 1.6 % had Bachelors, Masters, M.phill / Ms and Ph.D degree respectively. While 80.4 % of entrepreneurs has started their business after 2010.

d. Data Collection Tool

The questionnaire used in this research consists of four sections for different constructs is adopted for measurement (Burnell et al., 2021). Section A comprises the Personal profile of the entrepreneurs which comprises the entrepreneur's biographical information. For the Biographical profile, data was gathered related to the gender of the participants, their education level, and their experience as an entrepreneur. Further information was gathered related to their business like the name of the startup/ business, date of commencement of the business, what is the nature of the product dealt by an entrepreneur to set up a profile of the sample.

Section B consists of the questions related to Information network centrality. to measure the Information network centrality, five questions were asked from entrepreneurs which comprise questions like, How many people do you contact for getting information related to their business, competitors, customers, product and in an uncertain situation. According to Hanneman

and Riddle (2005), there is no wrong and right method to collect data related to Information network centrality instead focus of the researcher is to collect complete data conveniently in a cost and time-effective way.

Section C, consists scale of Entrepreneurial hustle, using a 6-point Likert scale with endpoints ranging from “strongly disagree (1) to strongly agree (6)” was adopted from (Burnell et al., 2021). Two components are related to Entrepreneurial hustle which is urgency and unorthodoxy. Urgency consists of 1-7 items and unorthodoxy measured through 8-14 items.

Section D consists close-ended, structured scale of Positive psychological capital, using a 6-point Likert scale with endpoints ranging from “strongly agree (6) to strongly disagree (1)” adopted by Luthans et al. (2007) attain the aim of the research. Positive psychological capital consists of 12 items to measure the construct. Positive psychological capital consists of four components which are hope self-efficacy, resilience, and optimism. Hope is measured from 1-3 items, efficacy from 4-7 items, resilience from 8-10 items, and optimism from 11-12 items.

5. Analysis of Data and Results

a. Data screening, Cleaning, and Transformation

Data were checked for missing values and to check the unengaged responses, the standard deviation was calculated for each respondent. Outliers were checked through the cook’s distance method and influential cases were deleted from the data. Data analysis was performed using SMART PLS because the SEM technique is used to describe the relationship between multiple variables simultaneously. It is the second generation technique of multivariate data analysis. This technique covers the weakness of conventional methods. In addition, it does not bind the researcher to fulfill the normality condition for data analysis and it reduces the error term in path relationships (Zhao, 2017). PLS-SEM consists of measurement model and structural model analysis to evaluate the model. In measurement model analysis, reliability and validity of the

outer layer variables are calculated and in structural model analysis, the path coefficient is calculated using the technique of bootstrapping (Irfan, 2021).

b. Measurement Model

The relationship between construct and indicator variable is displayed by the measurement model. Reliability analysis is the first component of the measurement model. Two methods are widely used to measure the reliability of the construct one is Cronbach's Alpha and the second one is composite Reliability. Composite Reliability is defined as the consistency of the items or factors to measure the underlying latent construct. Composite reliability is calculated through factor loadings. Previously, Cronbach Alpha was the most widely used technique to measure reliability but nowadays, composite reliability statistics along with Cronbach's Alpha are used together to report reliability in research because Cronbach Alpha as a measure of reliability faces criticism as it is not an adequate measure of reliability alone (Cronbach & Shavelson, 2004).

According to Ringle et al. (2020) cut of value for composite reliability is 0.70. As shown in Table 1, all the values of composite reliability statistics ranged from 0.874 to 0.969. Whereas Cronbach's Alpha ranged from 0.843 to 0.958, which is above the threshold value of 0.70, which demonstrates that all the latent constructs of the model achieved construct reliability.

Convergent validity is the second component of the measurement model. Convergent validity is defined as the degree to which many items of the construct are in agreement to measure the same construct or they are coming together to measure the same construct (Bagozzi et al., 1991). Convergent value calculated by Average Variance extracted (AVE). According to Ringle et al. (2020), the threshold value for AVE is 0.50. The AVE value above 0.50 is considered acceptable and below 0.50 is considered weak convergent validity. As indicated in Table 1, constructs attained convergent validity as values are above the cut-off criterion value of AVE.

Discriminate validity is measured through Heterotrait Monotrait (HTMT) ratio procedure. According to Henseler et al. (2015), the threshold value for HTMT to check the discriminant validity is less than or equal to 0.90. In this study as shown in Table 2, all the values fulfill the criteria so Discriminant validity is established.

Table 1.

Factors Loadings: Reliability and Validity

	A	Alpha	CR	AVE
Entrepreneurial hustle		0.855	0.881	0.571
EH1	0.678			
EH2	0.676			
EH3	0.699			
EH4	0.703			
EH5	0.775			
EH6	0.765			
EH7	0.701			
EH8	0.692			
EH9	0.688			
EH10	0.803			
EH11	0.727			
EH12	0.691			
EH13	0.729			
EH14	0.713			
Information network centrality		0.958	0.969	0.888
Info1	0.761			
Info2	0.794			
Info3	0.779			
Info4	0.714			
Info5	0.706			
Psycap		0.843	0.874	0.577
PPC_E1	0.804			
PPC_E2	0.825			
PPC_E3	0.673			
PPC_E4	0.664			
PPC_H1	0.680			
PPC_H2	0.680			
PPC_H3	0.838			
PPC_O1	0.747			
PPC_O2	0.763			

PPC_R1	0.607
PPC_R2	0.801
PPC_R3	0.628

Note: EH; entrepreneurial hustle.

Table 2.

Discriminant Validity

Using HTMT

	Entre _hustle	Info	Pscycap
Entre _hustle			
Info	0.093		
Pscycap	0.7	0.08	
Info_ EH	0.162	0.900	0.238

c. Structural Model

The structural model explains the paths between the constructs of the study. H1 evaluates whether PsyCap is positively related to Entrepreneur hustle. The results of the study revealed that PsyCap has a significant relation with Entrepreneurial hustle ($B = 0.552$, $t = 7.614$, $p < 0.05$). Hence, H1 was supported.

H2 evaluates whether Information network centrality moderates the relationship between PsyCap and Entrepreneurial hustle. The results revealed that effect found positive and significant ($B = 0.158$, $t = 3.099$, $p < 0.05$). Consequently, H2 is supported.

Table 3.

Hypotheses Testing

	Path coefficient	Standard deviation	T statistics	P value	Results
H1: Pscycap - > EH	0.552	0.073	7.614	0.000	Supported
H2: info - > EH	0.158	0.075	3.099	0.041	Supported

Note. info; Information network centrality.

6. Discussion

Entrepreneurship does not start and end with starting or founding a new business, instead ensuring the success and survival of the new business is the most important thing and the entrepreneur's responsibilities are more crucial in the whole process. The success of the venture depends on the total investment of the entrepreneur which is the summation of tangible and intangible resources. Intangible resources include his efforts and psychological resources. Entrepreneurial efforts depend on the entrepreneur's actions which he takes in the context of uncertainty (Baluku et al., 2018). Entrepreneur's specific actions, why, how, and when lead to venture success and failure. Why entrepreneurs hustle in a condition of uncertainty is the hallmark of an entrepreneur's action which leads to efforts. Further, Positive psychological capital is an individual's psychological capacity that can be measured, developed, and managed. Positive psychological capital is composed of four factors, Hope, Efficacy, Resilience, and optimism (Luthans et al., 2007)

This research sets out to explain the relationship between Positive psychological capital, Information network centrality, and Entrepreneurial hustle through mindset theory. The notion of Positive psychological capital was introduced in 2004 (Nolzen, 2018), and Entrepreneurial hustle in 2020 (Fisher et al., 2020), both concepts are new and no previous studies discuss the relationship between these variables.

As already discussed the goal of this study is to explain the relationship between Positive psychological capital and Entrepreneurial hustle and explain the moderation effect of Information network centrality on the relationship between Positive psychological capital and Entrepreneurial hustle. The result of this study is following the previous study that an entrepreneur's action is highly dependent on the mindset of entrepreneurs (Fisher et al., 2020) and how's one thinking or state of mind influences one's prosperity for entrepreneurial actions. This study found a significant positive relationship between Positive psychological capital and

Entrepreneurial hustle.

This study also found the significant moderation effect of Information network centrality on the relationship between Positive psychological capital and Entrepreneurial hustle. As discussed in previous studies (McMullen & Shepherd, 2006; Shane & Venkataraman, 2000) Information network centrality reduces the chances of irrelevant, and asymmetry information distribution in the context of uncertainty for better analyzing the world, capturing opportunities and better decisions in vague circumstances.

Finally, the finding of this study provide important theoretical insights and contribute to the body of literature by expanding the literature on how Positive psychological capital relate to Entrepreneurial hustle moderated by Information network centrality. The relationship between these construct is discussed first time in this study and need further exploration.

Conclusion

This study seeks to find the relationship between Positive psychological capital and Entrepreneurial hustle in Balochistan, Pakistan. The basis of the theoretical model is theorized from the assessment of relevant literature, particularly on Positive psychological capital, Entrepreneur hustle, degree centrality, and mindset theory. The research model demonstrates the association between all the constructs of the study. The variables of the research are defined. Positive psychological capital is composed of four factors, Hope, Efficacy, Resilience, and optimism (Luthans et al., 2007), and five concepts related to Entrepreneurial hustle are, hustle for resources, hustle for legitimacy, hustle for connections, hustle for learning and hustle for opportunity (Fisher et al., 2020) The link between constructs were established from literature into two research hypothesis. That directed this research and was significant. For hypothesis testing, the structural equation modeling (SEM) approach was used. It was found that Positive Psychology Capital is significantly positively related to Entrepreneurial hustle and Information

network centrality significantly positively strengthen the relationship between Positive Psychology Capital and Entrepreneurial hustle.

Recommendations

Entrepreneurs face challenges and are forced to take timely decisions in a context of uncertainty, to minimize the risk and enhance the quality of timely decisions positive psychological capital plays an important role. Entrepreneurs with high hope, self-efficacy, resilience, and optimism can create opportunities and take risks, accept challenges with courage, can tolerate pressure, and take advantage of timely decisions in the context of uncertainty. In addition, the main concern of entrepreneurs is relevant and reliable Information searching because it helps in better decision making by reducing irrelevant information and uncertainty. Positive psychological capital can be measured and developed, if the Entrepreneurs develop their positive psychological capital and information network centrality it helps in hustling entrepreneurship, which is the need of the modern world recent example of the uncertainty and hustling decision is pandemic COVID- 19.SO, it is suggested positive psychological capital and information network centrality enhance the decision's capability to capture opportunities and avoid risk.

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